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Efficient direct REcycling for low-valUe LFP battery for circular and Sustainable
waste management

D1.1 Battery waste type definitions and regulation

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

ADR	Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road
EOL	End of Life
GA	Grant agreement
GHS	Globally Harmonized System of classification and labelling of chemicals
LCO	Lithium cobalt oxide
LFP	Lithium iron phosphate
LMO	Lithium manganese oxide
NMC	Lithium (nickel, manganese, cobalt) oxide
NCA	Lithium (nickel, cobalt, aluminium) oxide
SDS	Safety data sheet

1. Executive summary

This report includes the main criteria for categorization of LFP batteries waste, which could be divided into two main categories: LFP (battery) production waste and EOL (End of Life) LFP battery. The LFP battery production waste is obtained during the production process as scrap at the end of life because of performance shortcoming. The EOL LFP battery falls below a certain failure threshold defined by the application and is no longer able to meet the performance demands. The parameters that are listed should be considered for each type of battery waste to achieve a safe and efficient recycling process.

In the meantime, it mentions how EU regulation covers the whole recycling process and where there are shortcomings. The content focuses mainly on the scrap and waste materials which will be employed in the "ReUse" project and finally the issues and concerns are discussed to define the safe way of transportation and recycling of LFP batteries.

2. Battery waste type definitions and regulation

2.1 Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are becoming more critical to many applications, including electric vehicles (EVs), electronic devices and portable powers due to their high energy density and long cycle life [1]. The demand volume of automotive LIBs reached 550 GWh worldwide in 2022 and these figures are expected to grow in a complex rate of 25% over in the upcoming years, as the clean energy technologies become increasingly crucial to the sustainability of human society [2, 3].

The rapid development in the production and application of the lithium-ion batteries has been continuously generating a substantial amount of production waste and end-of-life (EOL) LIBs since a decade ago, creating the challenge of developing a sustainable recycling strategy [4, 5]. The "ReUse" project aims to address the above challenge by developing a high-efficient recycling pathway for the battery waste in Europe (as shown in Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic and simplified illustration of the battery value chain. "ReUse" focuses on the green part of the value chain [6].

This report aims to obtain a clear and comprehensive understanding of battery waste, which facilitates the quick identification and safe handlings and transportations of battery waste in the "ReUse" project.

2.2 Current state and future of battery waste

2.2.1 Classification of batteries

Based on the rechargeability, the batteries can be classified into primary and secondary batteries. A primary battery is designed for a single use and cannot be recharged while a secondary battery is rechargeable and can be reused multiple time. Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are secondary batteries.

Batteries can also be classified based on their external shapes and casing materials. Common types of lithium-ion batteries used in power and energy storage include pouch, prismatic, and cylindrical cells.

Cylindrical cells (as shown in Figure 2) are characterized by the cylindrical shape and are known for their energy density and durability. The battery case is usually made of stainless steel. The cells are commonly used in consumer electronics such as laptops, power tools, and electric vehicles (EVs).

Figure 2. Cylindrical cells.

Prismatic cells (as shown in Figure 3) have a flat rectangular shape. They are favoured for their compact design and higher space utilization efficiency. Their battery case is usually made of aluminium. The main products of the two major battery manufacturers in the "ReUse" project, ElevenEs and Morrow, are prismatic cells. Their application in electric vehicles and energy storage increases rapidly.

Figure 3. Standard prismatic cell (left) and blade cell (right).

Pouch cells use a flexible pouch-like packaging that allows for customization of size and shape. They are frequently found in applications where space and weight are critical factors, such as EVs, drones and electronic devices. They use aluminium-plastic films as packaging.

Figure 4. Pouch cell.

Despite the significant differences in the appearance of these three types of batteries, the properties of LIBs mainly depend on its cathode chemistry, the cathodic active materials the battery uses. The major LIBs chemistries correspond to LCO, NMC/NCA, LMO, and LFP.

LCO batteries is the first chemistry system of LIBs. Due to its high voltage, LCO batteries are widely used in the consumer electronic field [7].

NMC batteries are widely used in EVs because of their high energy density and excellent complex performances including energy density, cycling performance and cost.

LMO batteries are used more in low-speed vehicles such as scooters since it has a lower energy density but a better high-temperature tolerance [7].

LFP batteries are widely applied in EVs and energy storage systems (ESS) due to their long cycle life, high safety, and relatively low cost.

The growth of LFP batteries accelerates with the emergence of blade batteries. The blade batteries are prismatic cells with high aspect ratio. It is favourably designed for electric vehicles, which utilize the space efficiency of the prismatic cells to compensate its lower energy density with LFP as cathode active materials.

2.2.2 General procedure of LIBs manufacturing

Generally, LIBs are made of a cathode, an anode, a separator, electrolyte, container and sealing parts [8]. The structure of a Li-ion cell is shown in ref. [9].

Take LFP prismatic cells for example. The cathode is an aluminium foil coated with cathode slurries which is a mixture of LFP, a conductive additive and a PVDF binder. Similarly, the anode consists of a mixture of graphite, a conductive additive, a polymer binder and a copper foil as the current collector. To prevent the direct physical contact between the cathode and anode, a separator made of polypropylene (PP), or polyethylene (PE) is placed between the anode and cathode to prevent short circuits [10]. The separator is a microporous membrane made from polyethylene or polypropylene which allows ions and solvents to pass through while still have enough mechanical strength to set apart the cathode and anode [10]. The electrolyte is a solution

of lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6) dissolved in an organic solvent, commonly carbonates such as PC (propylene carbonate), EC (ethylene carbonate), DEC (diethyl carbonate), DMC (dimethyl carbonate), or a mixture of these.

The materials compositions contained in LFP prismatic cells are summarized in table 1 [11].

Table 1. List of materials used in the LFP cell [11].

Name and registration number	Classification according to Regulation (EU) 1272/2008 (CLP)	Concentration (% w/w)
Lithium iron phosphate (CAS No: 15365-14-7)	476-700-9	35 – 45%
Graphite (CAS No: 7782-42-5)	231-955-3	15 - 25%
Copper (CAS No: 7440-50-8)	231-159-6	5-10%
Aluminium (CAS No: 7429-90-5)	231-072-3	5-10%
Poly (vinylidene fluoride) (CAS No:24937-79-9)	607-458-6	5-10%
Polypropylene (CAS Number 9003-07-0)	-	2-3%
Carbon black (CAS No:1333-86-4)	215-609-9	1-3%
Lithium hexafluorophosphate (CAS No:21324-40-3)	244-334-7	1-5%

Apart from the cathode active materials, the material composition of all the other lithium-ion batteries is similar. During discharge, lithium ions (Li^+) are transferred from the anode to the cathode by the electrolyte, while electrons (e^-) flow from the anode to the cathode through an external circuit, generating current. During charging, this process is reversed, with Li^+ ions moving from the cathode to the anode, and electrons flowing from the cathode to the anode through an external circuit [6]. Through the coordinated action of the battery components, the battery can store and release energy.

The manufacturing procedure of lithium-ion batteries varies for different battery shapes. However, regardless of the type, the production of lithium-ion batteries consists of three main stages; they are electrode manufacturing, cell assembly and electrolyte filling and packaging. Taking the production of a prismatic cells as an example, its manufacturing process is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Production process flow chart of a prismatic cell.

The general battery manufacturing process includes the following steps.

- i. **Slurry Mixing:** uniformly mixing cathodic or anodic active materials with other additives to form a slurry.
- ii. **Coating:** Continuously and evenly applying the slurry onto the surface of Al foil and Cu foil (current collectors), then drying to produce cathode and anode rolls.
- iii. **Calendaring:** Compacting the electrode rolls with a calendaring machine to achieve the desired density and thickness.
- iv. **Slitting and Notching:** Cutting the cathode and anode rolls into the specified size and shape that matches the cell, producing electrode sheets.

- v. **Stacking:** Using automatic or semi-automatic equipment to alternately stack the cathode sheets, separators, and anode sheets together in an orderly manner to form cell stacks.
- vi. **Welding:** Welding the Al and Cu tabs of each cathode and anode sheet together to form a cell stack.
- vii. **Insertion:** Put the cell stack into a cell case.
- viii. **Electrolyte Injection:** Injecting the electrolyte into the cell and ensuring the cell is fully soaked with the electrolyte. The cell stack must undergo dehydration before injection, and the injection process requires maintaining a certain low humidity.
- ix. **Formation:** Activating the active materials in the cathode and anode through several charge and discharge cycles, forming an SEI layer on the surface of the anode.
- x. **Top sealing:** Sealing the electrolyte injection port.
- xi. **Aging:** Sedating the cell at a certain temperature for a specific time to stabilize the SEI film.
- xii. **Grading:** Testing the capacity to select qualified cells.
- xiii. **Inspection:** Detecting defective products through OCV testing and assessing the state-of-charge (SOC) of the cell.
- xiv. **Warehousing:** Input the qualified cells in a warehouse.

Once the cells are made, different ways can be used to assemble multiple cells of the same type into a large aggregation, such as a module or a battery pack. The modules can be further assembled to form a battery pack for integrating into vehicles. The following picture shows the aggregation from cells to module until battery pack [12].

Figure 6. From cell through module and until battery pack [13].

2.2.3 The advantage and market share of LFP batteries

Previous sections introduce the different types of LIBs. Among LIBs, LFP batteries are employed in many application fields due to their excellent safety performance and long cycle life.

Right now, LFP batteries have a unique role in energy storage, EVs and commercial vehicles application. Pursuing the LFP batteries recycling as "ReUse" project by EU consortium shows the importance of these batteries. It's worth noting that a couple of the OEMs involved in the "ReUse" project are LFP battery manufacturers.

The superior safety of LFP cells relies on the stable polyanionic crystal structure. In fact, the LFP batteries owes their safety due to the strong P-O bonds. The crystal structure of LFP cathode active materials is highly stable and difficult to decompose, which prevents the collapse or the formation of highly oxidative substances, even under high temperatures or overcharging conditions [14]. On the other hand, LiFePO_4 undergoes a two-phase de-/lithiation process at approximately 3.5 V versus Li/Li^+ , providing an exceptionally stable voltage plateau. This contrasts with the single-phase intercalation process of layered oxide materials, which exhibit a sloped charge/discharge voltage profile [15].

The raw materials of LFP are also cheaper than NMC/NCA. Therefore, the LFP battery sale sees 100 times increase over the past decade [16]. According to the business investigation by

McKinsey, from 2020 to 2030, the LFP battery sales in Europe is expected to continuously increase 10 folds with a complex annual growth of 50% [17].

Figure 7. McKinsey predicted LFP battery market growth before 2030.

At the same time, several key OEM including battery manufacturer and vehicle groups, announce that their plans to build LFP battery production lines [18]. The "ReUse" project responds to this urging trend, focusing on the recycling and reuse of LFP batteries. Therefore, the focus of this report is on the definition and regulation of LFP batteries.

2.2.4 Estimation of LFP battery waste accumulation

Battery waste refers to discarded batteries and/or their components that are no longer usable due to physical damage and/or depletion of the energy storage capacity of batteries [19].

By 2021, there were 16.5 million EVs on the roads, with sales capturing 9% of the global car market share [20]. At the same time, Bloomberg NEF has pointed out that the market share of

LFP batteries in the global electric vehicle market has rapidly expanded over the past few years, growing from less than 10% in 2018 to nearly 40% in 2022 [21]. This trend is expected to continue in the future.

It is obvious that the amount of LFP battery waste will be proportional to the battery production and sale. Since 2019, China has been the largest market for electric vehicles and the leading manufacturer of batteries. It is predicted that by 2030, the total amount of spent batteries in China will reach 605,800 tons, with approximately 313,300 tons coming from spent LiFePO₄ batteries [22].

In 2023, European market accounted for 25% of the global electric vehicle sales, second only to China's 37% [23]. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that by 2030 the LFP battery waste in Europe will accumulate rapidly and the amount of LFP battery waste will achieve 200,000 tons.

2.3 Current state and prospect of Battery recycling

Batteries often contain one or multiple metals, along with organic or inorganic solutions, and a certain proportion of polymers. If released into the natural environment, they can cause serious environmental pollution and even pose risks to human health. Moreover, batteries are the most widely dispersed energy storage units in the human society. They are also among the most common consumables in daily life, and their accumulation over the years has led to a huge amount of battery waste. Therefore, battery waste must undergo rigorous and scientific treatment; careless disposal or incineration is unacceptable.

2.3.1 Current state and prospect of LIBs recycling market

Battery recycling is mainly implemented in China, US and Europe, which are also among the world's leading areas in terms of battery ownership and sales. Due to the economic value of the metals contained within batteries, battery recycling has been a well-established industry since the

beginning of this century. For example, in China, there are over 140 thousand enterprises related to the recycling of power batteries by the end of 2023 [24].

The economic values of typical LIBs components are listed in Table 2, where the cathode material constitutes approximately 90% of the total value of waste battery. Obviously, the estimation is based on the NMC batteries, as the value of Ni, Co, and Mn accounts for 70% of the total value of battery elements. Due to the technology complexity and intensive CAPEX [26] of battery recycling business, rigorous economy and technology feasibility studies are required before the implementation of a large-scale battery recycling project.

Table 2. The economic value of LIB components [25].

Component		Price (USD/tonne)		
		2001	2017	2019
Cathode	Al	1250	2000	1800
	Li	7500	9000	10000
	Co	38000	55000	35500
	Ni	8600	10000	13200
	Mn	1100	2000	2000
Anode	Cu	1800	5500	5800
	Graphite	550	1000	800

The recycling market for NMC batteries and some other batteries (such as LCO batteries, Ni-MH batteries, etc.) can be established because of the profits generated through the recycling process is sufficient to sustain the long-term development of mass recycling. However, compared to NMC batteries, LFP batteries, aside from Li, Cu, and Al, have most of their components either of low value, such as phosphorus salts, or challenging and costly to recycle and can only be landfilled or incinerated, such as graphite [27]. This significantly undermines the economic viability of recycling.

Despite a significant number of studies are available about materials recovery from waste LFP batteries, most of them are only applied at laboratory scale; very few can reach production level. However, the development of treatment processes for low-value batteries should be promoted and encouraged due to sustainability consideration. The strategic value of LFP battery components (such as Li, graphite and P) and the environmental hazards caused by improper disposal of LFP battery waste should be considered as indispensable sustainability aspects of the LFP battery recycling [27].

2.3.2 European regulations of battery waste and its recycling and their implementation

In Europe, the battery waste is mainly regulated by three directives: the Directive 2000/53/EC of the European Parliament [28] and of the Council of 18 September 2000 on end-of-life (EOL) vehicles, the Directive (EU) 2023/1542 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2023 on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators and the Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) [29].

Batteries installed in electric vehicles (EVs) are managed under the Directive 2000/53/EC until they are removed from the vehicle; once dismantled, they fall under the Directive (EU) 2023/1542. The WEEE Directive covers electrical and electronic equipment (EEE), including the batteries within these products. When EEE becomes waste and is dismantled for further treatment, batteries are collected separately for recycling, reuse, or repurposing and subsequently the Directive (EU) 2023/1542 [19] takes effect.

The Directive specifically addresses the waste management of five categories of batteries at their end of life:

- Portable battery < 5 kg
- Starting, lighting, or ignition batteries in vehicles (SLI)
- Electric vehicle (EV) battery
- Light means of transport (LMT) battery < 25 kg

Other industrial batteries

Different waste management obligations exist depending on the type of battery. According to the Directive (EU) 2023/1542, all five categories of batteries must be collected and recycled when they are no longer in use from end-users at no cost, irrespective of their nature, chemical composition, condition, brand, or origin. Despite these regulations, additional efforts are needed to improve collection efficiency and reduce the landfilling and incineration of spent lithium-ion batteries (LIBs).

Most European member states have met or exceeded the 2012 target for the collection of waste portable batteries, over 25% of waste portable batteries have been recycled; but only 14 member states have met the 2016 target (set at 45%). An estimated 56.7% of all waste portable batteries are not collected orderly, which hinders the achievement of the Directive's environmental protection objectives [30].

A significant limitation of collective recycling facilities around the world is their capacity, which can only process less than 30% of the world's LIB production [31]. Regarding LFP batteries, annual return flows of LFP batteries are expected to increase from 130 tonnes in 2017 to 310,000 tonnes in 2025 [32]. Similar data is reported by Circular Energy Storage Research and Consulting [33], as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. LIBs available for recycling in 2025 (tonnes) [33].

2.3.3 Overview of LIBs Recycling Technologies

Battery recycling is a process of separating and purifying various LIBs’ components through mechanical, chemical, high-temperature, and physical methods, or a combination of these methods, based on the differing physical and chemical properties of each component. Currently, there are five main technology routes for LIB recycling. Figure 9 summarizes the advantages and characteristics of the five recycling technologies.

Technology	Technology Readiness	Environmental aspects		Human health	Energy usage	Total cost	Revenue
		Global warming	Air/water pollution				
Pyrometallurgy	+++++	+	+	++	+	+	++++
Hydrometallurgy	+++	+++	+++	+	+++	+++	++++
Direct recycling	+++	+++++	+++++	+++++	++++	++++	+++++
Bioleaching	++	++++	++++	+++	+++++	+++++	++
Electrometallurgy	+++	+++++	++++	+++	+++++	++	+++

Best Worst

Figure 9. Comparison of different LIB recycling methods [34].

2.3.3.1 Pyrometallurgy

Pyrometallurgy, a widely used extractive metallurgy technique, has seen extensively developed in the battery recycling. When using traditional pyrometallurgical processes (such as direct roasting) to recycle waste LIBs, various components of lithium-ion batteries (i.e., cathode, anode, binder, separator, and electrolyte) are converted into alloy, slag, and gas at operating temperatures above 1000 °C. Alloys are typically collected as valuable products, while slag and gas are treated as waste [35].

2.3.3.2 Hydrometallurgy

Hydrometallurgy is widely used to recover valuable components from LIBs using various aqueous solutions (e.g., acids). Compared to pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy is more mature in recovering lithium components, offering various advantages during leaching and purification processes, including high recovery efficiency, high selectivity, low energy consumption, and reduced gas emissions. However, from a sustainability perspective, the use of strong acids and the handling of liquid waste pose significant challenges. Hydrometallurgy has evolved from Hydro 1.0 to Hydro 4.0, corresponding to inorganic acid and alkali leaching (Hydro 1.0), organic acid and solvent leaching and extraction (Hydro 2.0), integrated leaching and extraction (Hydro 3.0), and sustainable utilization (Hydro 4.0) [36].

2.3.3.3 Bio-metallurgy (Bioleaching)

Key factors affecting the performance of bioleaching processes include: (1) type of acidophilic microorganisms (bacteria vs. fungi), (2) pH and temperature, (3) nutrient or energy sources, (4) pulp density, (5) catalysts and particle size of waste LIB powder. Bioleaching technology is still limited to laboratory-scale research, primarily constrained by slow metal dissolution kinetics. Therefore, improving bio-leaching efficiency and achieving efficient selective dissolution of LIBs metals are the development directions [37].

2.3.3.4 Electrometallurgy

Compared to traditional methods like acid or alkali leaching, electrochemical metallurgy gains increasing attention for recovering metals from waste LIBs. Electrochemical processes use in-situ generated electrons as oxidants or reductants instead of exogenous chemicals used in other recycling technologies. Electrochemical-assisted leaching is considered environmentally friendly and more efficient than traditional aqueous leaching methods that require large amounts of reactants, high concentrations of acids, and high temperatures. Key factors influencing the performance of electrochemical metallurgy include: (1) current density/applied voltage; (2) electrolyte concentration; (3) leaching time, temperature, and mixing degree [38].

2.3.3.5 Direct Recycling

The main idea behind direct recycling strategies is to reactivate the cathodic/anodic active materials in waste batteries to restore the capacity and performance lost after the battery cycling. Major regeneration methods for cathode active materials include solid-state reactions, hydrothermal treatment and co-precipitation etc. but they all face challenges such as difficulty in impurity removal, high energy consumption, and complex reactions.

Apart from pyrometallurgy, the other four recycling methods mentioned above involve several critical steps, including discharging and disassembly, electrolyte recovery, separation of electrode materials and Cu/Al foils, and recycling or regeneration of electrode materials, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Key steps involved in the recycling of spent LIBs. Reproduced from [38].

2.4 Battery waste and battery recycling in the "ReUse" project

The battery waste in the "ReUse" project can be divided into two main categories based on its scrapping time and stage. One is production waste, which is the scraps and defective products generated during the battery production process, and the other is the EOL LFP batteries, which are used batteries that have reached the scrap standard.

Based on the different specifications in relation to the transportation and the safety of storage, handling, and processing, the battery waste stream at the same time can be categorized into four different quadrants as shown in Figure 11. Therefore, the regulations for the safety and transportation in Europe may be different.

The battery waste to be used and transported in the "ReUse" project include waste electrodes, battery parts, EOL batteries, etc., which are mainly in the solid state and corresponds to the battery waste of quadrants b, c and d.

Figure 11. Four quadrants of the battery waste stream. (a) wet waste without electrolyte contamination (waste slurries), (b) wet battery waste (containing electrolyte), (c) dry waste electrode, (d) black mass and shredded scraps.

The battery production waste to be transported and processed in the "ReUse" project come from two battery manufacturers, ElevenEs and Morrow Battery, as well as an electric vehicle OEM and battery integrator Kyburz. The EOL LFP batteries are sorted manually at Sortbat from a mixed EOL Li-ion battery waste for VITO to develop automated sorting technology based on sensory recognition on a multisensory characterization device installed at Sortbat.

These battery wastes will form a waste stream flow, passing through different project partners, being progressively disassembled, decomposed and purified until they are regenerated to become high-performance raw materials and used in new LIBs.

All the recycling steps introduced in the previous section will be carried out by partners in the "ReUse" project. These steps include discharging, disassembly, electrolyte recovery, separation of the cathode, anode, and Al/Cu metals, and separation of the cathodic and anodic active materials. The project will also explore and utilize various recycling technologies, including direct recycling technique, electrochemical recycling, pyrometallurgy, and hydrometallurgy. The

specific recycling technologies used by each partner and the materials they recover will be described in Section 2.6.

2.5 Technical description and identification of battery waste in the "ReUse" project

The battery waste could be divided into two main categories: LFP (battery) production waste and EOL (End of Life) LFP battery. The former is generated in the process stream of the LFP battery production, while the latter refers to the finished battery products which have reached EOL. This section describes technical descriptions and identification specifications of the battery waste that will be investigated and transported in the "ReUse" project.

A clear and accurate definition of battery waste can provide valuable knowledge for other research topics of the "ReUse" project, such as sorting and AI identification. Additionally, it can help facilitate the smooth cross-border transportation of battery waste in Europe, ensuring that the waste is safely and legally stored and handled in the laboratories or factories of the project partners.

Although the types of battery waste vary depending on the physical or chemical type, the principles of recycling and reuse are the same; this involves separating and purifying the materials in the waste through various methods such as mechanical, chemical, and high-temperature processes etc., based on the differing technical properties of these components. Understanding the characteristics and physio-chemical properties of each waste type allows us to explore efficient recycling methods.

2.5.1 Battery production and waste stream

Most of the LIBs production consists of the following process steps: slurry mixing, electrode (both anode and cathode) coating, calendaring, cutting, cell assembling, electrolyte filling, formation, packaging, aging, and testing. For different types of the lithium-ion batteries, the

parameters are different for each process step. However, as shown in Figure 12, the types of production waste generated during the battery manufacturing process and their corresponding process steps are usually similar.

Figure 12. Battery waste stream in the LIB production.

On the other hand, the EOL batteries can be classified according to their types, for instance, the EOL LFP, NMC and LCO batteries, and/or the EOL prismatic, pouch and cylindrical batteries etc.

The "ReUse" project focuses on LFP battery recycling, with LFP prismatic batteries from two partners who are OEM manufacturers. Therefore, defining the battery waste based on LFP prismatic batteries has practical reasons. In addition, these definitions could also be used as a reference for the battery waste coming from a broader range of LIBs.

Next, each section will introduce ONE type of battery waste together with its physio-chemical properties.

Table 1 has listed the materials used in the LFP prismatic battery. These materials become part of the battery composition through the battery manufacturing process and subsequently become part of the battery waste. Correspondingly, the materials contained in each waste will affect its reactivity, chemical stability and safety characteristics.

2.5.2 Technical description of waste cathode (sheet)

Waste cathode is a defective or scrap roll or sheet generated during the cathode manufacturing or cell assembling.

From the appearance (Figure 13), a cathode roll/sheet is a composite sheet of less than 1 mm in thickness and consists of aluminium foil and double-coated cathode materials layer. In the "ReUse" project, the dimension of the waste cathode is between 0.1 to 1 m in length, 0.1 to 0.2 m in width, and 100 to 500 μm in thickness.

One or both sides of the cathode sheets are smooth or matte, dark grey to black in colour, with a silver colour tab on one of the long ends of the cathode. The waste cathode sheets used in the "ReUse" project are illustrated.

Figure 13. Waste cathode sheets from “ReUse” Project partners (a) ElevenEs, (b) schematic structure and (c) Morrow LFP cathode waste.

The primary component of the cathode sheet is lithium iron phosphate cathodic active material (LFP).

In the "ReUse" project, the waste cathode sheet may be single- or double-layer coated, and the coating may not be uniform or complete. Therefore, the mass fraction of LFP in the waste cathode ranges from 55 wt.%-80 wt.%. Additionally, the waste cathode may have undergone calendaring or not, resulting in a glossy or non-glossy reflection.

The second main component of waste cathode sheet is aluminium, which accounts for 15 wt.%-40 wt.%.

The remaining components are mainly binder and conductive additives in the cathode material such as PVDF and Super-P carbon. Similarly, if the coating is ununiform or incomplete, the weight percentage of these materials will change.

The physical and chemical properties of the waste cathode also depend on the abovementioned material compositions.

In general, the cathode waste should be stable under normal conditions, but avoiding excess heat or fire, dust formation, and exposure to moist air or water. At temperatures over 150 °C, PVDF will melt. This leads to the disintegration or brittleness of the electrode sheet. Under fire conditions, hazardous decomposition products such as carbon oxides, hydrogen fluoride may form. Fumes of aluminium or aluminium oxide may also emit at high temperature. Exposure to moist air, water, or dust formation will accelerate the oxidation of aluminium, causing the increase of the waste's weight and a loss of aluminium metal [39,40,41].

2.5.3 Waste anode (sheet)

Waste anode is a defective or scrap roll or sheet generated during the electrode manufacturing or cell assembling.

The waste anode roll/sheet is a composite sheet of less than 1 mm in thickness and consists of copper current collector and anode materials layer. In the "ReUse" project, the dimension of the waste anode is generally between 0.1 to 1 m in length, 0.1 to 0.2 m in width, and 100 to 300 µm

in thickness. In appearance, one or both sides of the waste anode are smooth or matte black, with a copper tab on one of the long ends of the anode. Some waste anode sheets from the "ReUse" project partners are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Waste anode sheets from “ReUse” Project partners (a) ElevenEs LFP waste anode, (b) schematic structure and (c) Morrow of LFP waste anode.

The primary component of the fully coated anode waste is graphite, accounting for 30 wt.% - 55 wt.%. The second main component is copper, accounting for 40 wt.% - 65 wt.%. The remaining components are mainly binders and conductive additives such as SBR and Super-P [42] carbon. If the coating is ununiform or incomplete, the proportion of anode materials, including graphite, will change.

The physical and chemical properties of the anode waste also depend on the abovementioned material compositions.

In general, the anode waste should be stable at ambient temperatures and pressures but avoiding all possible sources of ignition (spark or flame), excess heat, dust formation, and exposure to moist air or water. At temperature over 140 °C, SBR start melting and producing smoke and fumes, which possess irritancy potential. In addition, potentially hazardous decomposition products such as carbon oxides formed and emitted under fire conditions. Fumes of aluminium or aluminium oxide may emit at high temperature. High temperature, exposure to moist air and water and dust formation can facilitate copper to deteriorate to copper oxide or dissolvable salts, resulting in the loss or degradation of Cu.[43-45]

2.5.4 Waste electrode stack

Waste electrode stack is a defective or scrap stack mainly generated during the cell assembly section of the battery production, which includes stacking, hot pressing, welding and stack insertion.

The waste electrode stack is formed by stacking multiple cathode and anode sheets along with separators in between.

In the "ReUse" project, the thickness of the stack is usually several mm up to 3 mm, and its length and width are equivalent to those of the cathodes or anodes. In appearance, the waste electrode stack typically has multiple copper and aluminium tabs protruding out from one end of the stack's length respectively. Additionally, white or opaque polymer films or wrappings can be seen in between or around the edges of the electrodes. Some waste electrode stacks from the "ReUse" project partners are shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Waste electrode stack from "ReUse" project partners (a) ElevenEs and (b) Morrow.

The primary component of the waste electrode stack is LFP, accounting for 50 wt.% - 60 wt.%. The second main component is graphite, accounting for 20 wt.% - 30 wt.%, and the metal components copper, aluminium each account for 4 – 9 wt.%.

However, unlike the waste electrode, the physical and chemical properties of the waste stack are significantly influenced not only by these main components but also by the PP/PE separator,

which accounts for less than 5% of its total weight. Since PP/PE is the most flammable component and has the lowest melting point among all the components of the stack, it determines the specifications regarding the safe storage, handling, and transportation of stack waste.

The waste stack is chemically stable under recommended conditions of storage, use and temperature. Whether during storage, transportation, or mechanical processing of the electrode stack, direct contact with strong oxidizing or reducing agents must be avoided. Upon exposure to fire or excess heat ($>135\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), toxic and harmful gases such as carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide can be released, accompanied by a pungent odour. SDS of the electrode stack is currently unavailable, while SDS of separator is listed in the reference part.[46]

2.5.5 Waste dry cell

Waste dry cell is a defective or scrap cell generated near the end of the cell assembly section, which corresponds to stack insertion and lid welding.

A waste dry cell consists of a cell case and the stack inside. In the “ReUse” project, the dry cell's dimensions are slightly larger than those of the electrode stack. The main increase is the size of the cell case and around 2 cm space for accommodating the welding tabs to both ends of the stack. Externally, a waste dry cell has a silver metal casing, typically made of aluminium. On two opposite end surfaces, or on opposite sides of one end surface, there are positive and negative terminals that welded to the tabs internally and attached to the end surfaces. Some dry cells from the "ReUse" project partners are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Waste dry cells from ReUse project partners (a) ElevenEs and (b) Morrow Battery.

The component of the dry cell is like that of the stack, with the addition of an aluminium battery casing and lids.

Due to the external aluminium casing as a support, the dry cell has better resistance to mechanical impact and overheat compared to the bare cell stack, as well as the ability to resist chemical attack.

However, during storage, transportation of the waste dry cell, the dry cell should not come in contact with strong oxidizing agent, acid or alkaline, as the aluminium casing is susceptible to corrosion by these chemicals.

In addition, the dry cell should avoid exposure to fire or excess heat (>135 °C), since toxic and harmful gases such as carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide can be released, which may also cause the battery swelling.

2.5.6 Waste wet cell

Waste cell is a defective cell or an EOL battery with depleted energy storage capacity. A defective waste cell is usually generated in the latter sections of the production, which includes electrolyte filling, aging, formation, OCV and grading, testing and inspection, and sorting.

A waste wet cell, which is filled with electrolyte, can be an unfinished or finished product. In the "ReUse" project, the wet cell's dimensions are almost the same as the waste dry cell.

Compared to dry cells, wet batteries may have external packaging, labels, and other manufacturing information. A typical wet cell from ElevenEs is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Waste cells (wet) from “ReUse” project partners.

The components of the waste wet cell are identical with a full battery product, which had already been listed in the table 1.

Considering the physical and chemical properties related to safety, waste wet cells are mainly divided into two types: sealed wet cells and unsealed wet cells. The unsealed wet cells should be welded and sealed to be treated as sealed waste wet cells for safe storage and transportation. The SDS of LFP battery is available in the annex of this report. According to SDS:

Waste cells should be well separated to prevent short circuit and packed in a strong package during transport.

Waste cells should incorporate a safety venting device or be designed to prevent a violent rupture under normal transport conditions.

Waste cells should be kept away from high temperature and open flames.

Waste cells must be offered for transport at a state of charge (SoC) not exceeding 30% of their rated design capacity.

2.5.7 Waste battery lid and other components

In addition to waste containing cathodic/anodic active materials, the LIBs production also generates scraps of battery components (Figure 18), such as battery case, battery lids, and separator films. Some of this waste will also be collected and analysed by the "ReUse" project partners.

The physical and chemical properties and safety characteristics of these components are consistent with the materials of those battery parts, such as aluminium used for battery case and the polymers of PE/PP for separators. The SDS of these non-active battery materials is cited in the reference part. [47]

Figure 18. (a) Battery case from ElevenEs, (b) battery lid from Morrow Battery.

2.5.8 The definition of battery waste in the EU regulation

In the EU regulation, although there is no specific and technical definition for each type of the battery waste such as: cathode waste, anode waste and stack etc, in the regulation (EU) 2023/1542 [19], a general waste term has been defined such as “waste” and “battery manufacturing waste”. Based on the article 3, point 50 of the regulation (EU) 2023/1542, ‘waste battery’ means any battery which is waste as defined in Article 3, point (1), of Directive 2008/98/EC [51]; in point (51) of the same article and regulation, also mentioned that ‘battery manufacturing waste’ means the materials or objects rejected during the battery manufacturing process, which cannot be re-used as an integral part in the same process and need to be recycled; it should be noted that Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2023 concerning batteries and waste batteries, amending Directive 2008/98/EC and Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Directive 2006/66/EC.

In Article 3, point (17), of Directive 2008/98/EC; ‘recycling’ means any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes. It includes the reprocessing of organic material but does not include energy recovery and the reprocessing into materials that are to be used as fuels or for backfilling operations. Also based on point (54) of article 3 of Regulation (EU) 2023/1542, ‘preparation for recycling’ means the treatment of waste batteries prior to any recycling process, including, inter

alia, the storage, handling and dismantling of battery packs or the separation of fractions that are not part of the battery itself.

In Annex XIII (Conformity assessment procedures) of regulation (EU) 2023/1542, a battery passport shall include the following information relating to the battery model, which shall be accessible only to persons with a legitimate interest and the Commission: detailed composition, including materials used in the cathode, anode and electrolyte.

Following the instruction of the regulation (EU) 2023/1542 about the battery passport, this report also prepares the data, definition and methodology for the passport specification for future reference.

2.6 The flow and processing of waste stream in the "ReUse" project

Figure 19. Overall methodology and project flow in ReUse [6].

As illustrated in Figure 19, with the materials flowing, the waste will be processed at the facilities of the partner which has the relevant expertise, ensuring that all the waste could be reused in the future.

Early in the project, battery manufacturers (ElevenEs/MB) supply production scraps, including waste electrodes and dry/wet rejected cells.

The EOL battery waste is collected and transferred to Sortbat's premises for automated characterization and sorting by multisensory device developed by VITO.

Later a mix of small and still charged packs/cells coming from the battery sorting facility at Sortbat will arrive at battery integrator KYBURZ for safe discharge. The deactivated battery pack will be transferred to DTI for the extraction of the cells.

Next the production waste and discharged cells will be disassembled, and the material composition of these waste will be separated by the crushing machine at ElevenEs or the automation robotics at Fraunhofer.

The separated material will be sent to and treated by different partners for the recycling of both active and non-active materials. Waste electrolyte will be extracted and purified at Arkema. In pilot recycling facility at DTI and Arkema, the binder will be extracted, purified and tested.

After extraction of the binder the black mass (a mixture of the powders) classification will be implemented at Fraunhofer using a cylindrical centrifuge. In the cascade process developed by Fraunhofer, the carbon black, cathode/anode materials and Al/Cu in the centrifugation will be collected separately.

In the next step, the active cathode materials will be regenerated in the facility of MB and ElevenEs. The active anode materials will be regenerated in the facility of EMPA and ElevenEs. The regenerated LFP and graphite will finally be returned to the two battery manufacturers ElevenEs and MB for testing.

The above-mentioned partners are in different European countries. To make sure the transportation, storage, and processing of the waste between partners are safe and compliant with regulations the following two sections will present the results of investigation and studies on these aspects to facilitate the smooth progress of the project.

3. Safety aspects related to storage, handling and processing of production waste and EOL batteries

In the "ReUse" project a large variety of different samples will be tested. This section describes the risks associated with the above materials, products and wastes, and provides guidelines for their storage, handling and possible processing.

3.1 LFP production waste

The LFP production waste materials, which are discussed in Section 2.5, bear risks related to the chemicals and materials (e.g. those reported in table 1 [11]) contained within such waste materials. Directive 2008/98/EC [51] contains a non-limited overview of the materials contained within different production waste materials. The risks of the waste streams can thus be approximated by the risks related to the individual chemicals that the material is composed of. Such evaluation however does not consider the risks that might arise from the combination/mixing of materials.

This section provides an overview of the risks related to the individual materials that LFP production waste, as well as a full LFP battery cell, is composed of (see Table 3). Each individual material is shortly described, and the main safety features, which are based on the safety data sheets (SDS) of such materials, will be highlighted. The hazard (H) and precautionary (P) statements of the substances are given according to the classification system of Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP).

Table 3. Overview of materials contained within LFP production waste streams.

LFP production waste	Water	LFP	Graphite	CNT	PVDF	Super P	NMP	CMC	SBR	Aluminium	Copper	PC solvent	LiPF ₆	EC	DMC	PP/PE	Al/Mn alloy
Cathode slurry																	
Anode slurry																	
Cathode electrode/roll																	
Anode electrode/roll																	
Waste water																	
Waste NMP																	
Pressed stack																	
Assembled dry cell																	
Wet battery cell																	
Al sheet/roll																	
Cu sheet/roll																	
Separator sheet/roll																	
Electrolyte																	
Al battery case																	

3.1.1 Identification of battery chemicals and materials

The CAS (Chemical Abstracts Service) registry numbers of the above listed chemicals are listed in CAS SciFinder® (48); see Table 4 for full names and CAS numbers.

Table 4. Full names and CAS registry numbers of chemicals that can be present in LFP batteries and their production wastes.

Abbreviation, description	Full name	Chemical formula	CAS registry number
LFP	Lithium iron phosphate	LiFePO ₄	15365-14-7
Graphite	Graphite	C	7782-42-5
CNT	Carbon nanotubes	C	308068-56-6
PVDF	Polyvinylidene fluoride	(CH ₂ CF ₂) _n	24937-79-9
Super P	carbon black powder for lithium-ion	C	1333-86-4
NMP	n-methyl-2-pyrrolidone	C ₅ H ₉ NO	872-50-4
CMC	Carboxymethylcellulose, sodium salt	 R = H or CH ₂ CO ₂ H	9004-32-4
SBR	1,3-butadiene/styrene, polymer	(C ₈ H ₈) _x (C ₄ H ₆) _y	9003-55-8
Aluminium		Al	7429-90-5

Copper		Cu	7440-50-8
PC	Propylene carbonate, 4-methyl-1,3-dioxolan-2-one	C ₄ H ₆ O ₃	108-32-7
LiPF ₆	Lithium hexafluorophosphate	LiPF ₆	21324-40-3
EC	Ethylene carbonate	C ₃ H ₄ O ₃	96-49-1
DMC	Dimethyl carbonate	C ₃ H ₆ O ₃	616-38-6
PP/PE	Polypropylenes/polyethylene		

3.1.2 Storage and handling

Storage and handling prescriptions of the above listed individual chemicals are described in their respective safety data sheets (SDSs). An overview of these prescriptions is given in the table below.

Table 5. Overview of handling and storage prescriptions of the individual chemicals present in LFP batteries and their production waste

Prescription	Water	LFP	Graphite	CNT	PVDF	Super P	NMP	CMC	SBR	Aluminium	Copper	PC solvent	LiPF ₆	EC	DMC	PP/PE	Al/Mn alloy
Personal protection																	
Protective gloves against chemicals (EN 374)		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Safety glasses (EN 166)		X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X		X			
Face shield (EN 166)							X						X				
In case of dust production: protective goggles (EN 166)			X	X	X			X	X	x			X	X			
Protective clothing (EN 14605 or EN 13034)		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X		X	X		
Corrosion-proof clothing (EN14605)													X				
Dust production: dust mask with filter type P1		X			X			X	X								
Dust production: dust mask with filter type P2			X	X										X			
Dust production: dust mask with filter type P3											X		X				
Full face mask with filter type A at conc. in air > exposure limit							X										
High dust production: self-contained breathing apparatus (EN 136 + EN 137)													X				
Materials for protective clothing																	
Butyl rubber			X				X					X		X			
Neoprene (chloroprene rubber)							P			X				X			
Nitrile rubber		X					P			X				X			
PVC			X				P			X		X		X			
Rubber			X		X		P			X		X					
Handling the product																	
Comply with the legal requirements			X	X	X		X	X	X			X	X	X	X		
Clean contaminated clothing			X	X	X		X		X			X	X	X	X		
Keep container tightly closed			X	X	X		X	X	X			X	X	X	X		

Powdered form: no compressed air for pumping over			X	X		X	X				X	X		
Do not discharge the waste into the drain						X	X				X	X		
Before use: check for peroxides and eliminate them						X								
Thoroughly clean/dry the installation before use							X					X		
Handle uncleaned empty containers as full ones												X		
Avoid raising dust			X	X	X		X	X			X	X		
Keep away from naked flames/heat			X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	
In finely divided state: use spark-/explosionproof appliances			X		X	X	X	X		X		X		
Finely divided: keep away from ignition sources/sparks			X		X	X	X	X		X		X	X	
Take precautions against electrostatic charges					X			X					X	
At temperature > flashpoint: use spark-/explosionproof appliances						X								
Use earthed equipment						X				X				
Observe very strict hygiene – avoid contact											X			
Observe strict hygiene			X			X						X		
Observe normal hygiene standards	X		X	X			X	X	X	X			X	
Carry operations in the open/under local exhaust/ventilation or with respiratory protection	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Measure the concentration in the air regularly				X		X	X						X	
Materials for packaging														
Synthetic material			X			P								
Wood			X											
Textile			X											
Paper			X							P				
Steel						X								
Stainless steel						X								
Nickel						X								
glass						X								
Plastics											X			
Containers: special requirements														
Closing	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Correctly labelled			X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	

Meet the legal requirements			X	X	X		X	X	X			X	X	X	X		
Secure fragile packaging in solid containers			X	X	X		X	X	X			X	X	X	X		
Opaque							X										
Clean									X							X	
Dry																X	
Storage																	
Meet the legal requirements		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		
Aboveground														X			
Store at room temperature							X				X	X					
Store in a cool area		X		X				X		X	X	X					
Store in a dark area							X										
Store in a dry area		X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Keep container in a well-ventilated place		X		X			X		X	X	X	X					
May be stored under nitrogen							X					X					
May be stored under argon												X					
Keep out of direct sunlight									X			X					
Provide the tank with earthing									X							X	
Ventilation at floor level																X	
Fireproof storeroom																X	
Provide for a tub to collect spills																X	
Prohibitions on mixed storage (keep away from)																	
Heat sources			X	X	X		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X		
Ignition sources			X		X			X	X		X			X	X		
Oxidizing agents			X		X		X		X		X	X	X	X	X		
Reducing agents											X			X	X		
(strong) acids							X	X	X			X	x	X	X		
(strong)bases							X					X		X	X		
Water/moisture							X				X	X					
halogens			X														
Combustible materials									X								

P: poor resistance

3.1.3 Classification and labelling according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008

Some of the above listed chemicals are classified according to the criteria of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008. The chemicals that are classified according to this regulation are described below and their hazard (H) and precautionary (P) statements are given.

3.1.3.1 Carbon nanotubes (CNT)

The material Carbon nanotubes (CNT) is **classified as dangerous** according to the criteria of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008.

- Hazard statements:
 - H319: Causes serious eye irritation.
 - H335: May cause respiratory irritation.
- Precautionary statements:
 - P101: If medical advice is needed, have product container or label at hand.
 - P102: Keep out of reach of children.
 - P280: Wear eye protection.
 - P261: Avoid breathing dust.
 - P271: Use only outdoors or in a well-ventilated area.
 - P264: Wash hands thoroughly after handling.
 - P304 + P340: IF INHALED: Remove person to fresh air and keep comfortable for breathing.
 - P305 + P351 + P338: IF IN EYES: Rinse cautiously with water for several minutes. Remove contact lenses, if present and easy to do. Continue rinsing.
 - P337 + P313: If eye irritation persists: Get medical advice/attention.
 - P312: Call a POISON CENTER/doctor if you feel unwell.
 - P403 + P233: Store in a well-ventilated place. Keep container tightly closed.
 - P405: Store locked up.

- P501: Dispose of contents/container in accordance with local/regional/national/international regulation.

3.1.3.2 Super P: carbon black powder for LIBs

The material is catalogued with CAS-No 1333-86-4. It is not a hazardous substance or mixture for the GHS classification.

3.1.3.3 N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP)

N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) is **classified as dangerous** according to the criteria of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008.

- Hazard statements:
 - H360D: May damage the unborn child.
 - H315: Causes skin irritation.
 - H319: Causes serious eye irritation.
 - H335: May cause respiratory irritation.
- Precautionary statements:
 - P101: If medical advice is needed, have product container or label at hand.
 - P102: Keep out of reach of children.
 - P202: Do not handle until all safety precautions have been read and understood.
 - P280: Wear eye protection.
 - P271: Use only outdoors or in a well-ventilated area.
 - P264: Wash hands thoroughly after handling.
 - P304 + P340: IF INHALED: Remove person to fresh air and keep comfortable for breathing.
 - P302 + P352: IF ON SKIN: Wash with plenty of water and soap.
 - P332+313: If skin irritation occurs: Get medical advice/attention.
 - P362+364: Take off contaminated clothing and wash it before reuse.
 - P305 + P351 + P338: IF IN EYES: Rinse cautiously with water for several minutes. Remove contact lenses, if present and easy to do. Continue rinsing.

- P337 + P313: If eye irritation persists: Get medical advice/attention.
- P308+313: If exposed: Call a POISON CENTER or doctor/physician.
- P312: Call a POISON CENTER/doctor if you feel unwell.
- P403 + P233: Store in a well-ventilated place. Keep container tightly closed.
- P405: Store locked up.
- P501: Dispose of contents/container in accordance with local/regional/national/international regulation.

3.1.3.4 Propylene carbonate (PC)

Propylene carbonate (4-methyl-1,3-dioxolan-2-one) is **classified as dangerous** according to the criteria of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008

- Hazard statements:
 - H319: Causes serious eye irritation.
- Precautionary statements:
 - P101: If medical advice is needed, have product container or label at hand.
 - P102: Keep out of reach of children.
 - P280: Wear eye protection.
 - P264: Wash hands thoroughly after handling.
 - P305 + P351 + P338: IF IN EYES: Rinse cautiously with water for several minutes. Remove contact lenses, if present and easy to do. Continue rinsing.
 - P337 + P313: If eye irritation persists: Get medical advice/attention.

3.1.3.5 Lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF₆)

Lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF₆) is **classified as dangerous** according to the criteria of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008.

- Hazard statements:
 - H301: Toxic if swallowed.
 - H372: Causes damage to organs (bones, teeth) through prolonged or repeated exposure.

- H314: Causes severe skin burns and eye damage.
- Precautionary statements:
 - P101: If medical advice is needed, have product container or label at hand.
 - P102: Keep out of reach of children.
 - P280: Wear protective gloves, protective clothing and eye protection/face protection.
 - P260: Do not breathe dust/fume/gas/mist/vapours/spray.
 - P264: Wash hands thoroughly after handling.
 - P270: Do not eat, drink or smoke when using this product.
 - P304 + P340: IF INHALED: Remove person to fresh air and keep comfortable for breathing.
 - P303 + P361 + P353: IF ON SKIN (or hair): Take off immediately all contaminated clothing. Rinse skin with water or shower.
 - P363: Wash contaminated clothing before reuse.
 - P305 + P351 + P338: IF IN EYES: Rinse cautiously with water for several minutes. Remove contact lenses, if present and easy to do. Continue rinsing.
 - P301 + P330 + P331: IF SWALLOWED: rinse mouth. Do NOT induce vomiting.
 - P310: Immediately call a POISON CENTER/doctor.
 - P405: Store locked up.
 - P501: Dispose of contents/container in accordance with local/regional/national/international regulation.
 - P370 + P378: In case of fire: Use suitable extinguishing medium to extinguish.

3.1.3.6 Ethylene carbonate (EC)

Ethylene carbonate is **classified as dangerous** according to the criteria of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008.

- Hazard statements:
 - H302: Harmful if swallowed.

- H373: May cause damage to organs (kidneys) through prolonged or repeated exposure if swallowed.
 - H319: Causes serious eye irritation.
- Precautionary statements:
 - P101: If medical advice is needed, have product container or label at hand.
 - P102: Keep out of reach of children.
 - P280: Wear eye protection.
 - P260: Do not breathe dust.
 - P264: Wash hands thoroughly after handling.
 - P270: Do not eat, drink or smoke when using this product.
 - P305 + P351 + P338: IF IN EYES: Rinse cautiously with water for several minutes. Remove contact lenses, if present and easy to do. Continue rinsing.
 - P337 + P313: If eye irritation persists: Get medical advice/attention.
 - P330: Rinse mouth.
 - P301 + P312: IF SWALLOWED: Call a POISON CENTRE/doctor if you feel unwell.
 - P501: Dispose of contents/container in accordance with local/regional/national/international regulation.

3.1.3.7 Dimethylcarbonate (DMC)

Dimethylcarbonate (DMC) is **classified as dangerous** according to the criteria of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008.

- Hazard statements:
 - H225: Highly flammable liquid and vapour.
- Precautionary statements:
 - P102: Keep out of reach of children.
 - P210: Keep away from heat, hot surfaces, sparks, open flames and other ignitions sources. No smoking.

- P243: Take action to prevent static discharges.
- P280: Wear protective gloves and eye protection/face protection.
- P233: Keep container tightly closed.
- P303 + P361 + P353: IF ON SKIN (or hair): Take off immediately all contaminated clothing. Rinse skin with water or shower.
- P370 + P378: In case of fire: Use suitable extinguishing medium to extinguish.
- P403 + P235: Store in a well-ventilated place. Keep cool.
- P501: Dispose of contents/container in accordance with local/regional/national/international regulation.

To summarize what is listed in this section, the materials used to make LFP batteries are hazardous:

H315: Causes skin irritation

H319: Causes eye irritation

H225: Highly flammable liquid and vapour

H335: Causes respiratory irritation

H372: Causes damages to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure

The precautionary actions are advised for handling:

P210: keep away from heat, hot Surfaces, sparks, open flames and other ignition sources. No smoking

P243: Take action to prevent static discharges

P261: Avoid breathing dust

P264: Wash hands thoroughly after handling

P270: Do not eat, drink or smoke when using this product

P271: Use in a well-ventilated area

P280: Wear protective gloves, protective clothing and eye/face protection

The precautionary actions are advised for storage:

P403 + P233: Store in a well-ventilated place. Keep container tightly closed

P403 + P235: Store in a well-ventilated place. Keep cool

P405: Store locked up

3.2 Li-ion batteries and related materials

The use of lithium batteries has increased significantly everywhere in recent years. LIBs can store large amounts of energy, making them indispensable in many consumer products, from electric cars to laptops, that the public uses daily. While these batteries offer many benefits of an effective source of power, they also carry risks. When they are damaged, encountering water, improperly used, charged, or stored, the likelihood of them short-circuiting, overheating, and catching fire is real. If the flammable ingredients in lithium batteries, such as nickel, organic electrolyte solvents, or polymers catch fire, bright fires and toxic smoke release will occur.

A LIB fire poses great threats and risks to both human health and the environment. It releases corrosive and toxic substances such as chemicals and heavy metals that can cause severe burns and injury and lithium poisoning. Extinguishing battery fires can create toxic firewater. This poses a danger to firefighters, emergency responders, workers and nearby residents. Therefore, it is important to prevent a battery fire. This means eliminating the possibility of the occurrence of a fire or explosion hazards which can arise from various causes:

- Damage to energy carrier by falling (by far the most important cause)
- Manufacturing error in energy carrier
- Error during loading process in storage
- Aging during storage
- Internal and external short circuit
- Lightning strike
- External radiation (fire)
- Mechanical impact from outside
- Influence by other substances (mixed storage)

Fire in a storage facility is dangerous and unnecessary when it could have been prevented. Unfortunately, it does occur, for example when safety precaution has not been sufficiently taken. The storage and handling during processing of these batteries involve specific risks. For example, short circuits and thermal runaway can occur, which is an unwanted chemical process in which the temperature of a battery cell goes haywire and rises significantly. A fire can occur, releasing toxic gases. It is also possible for batteries to explode under certain conditions.

3.2.1 PGS37-2 Dutch regulation of storage lithium batteries

An important step in preventing battery fires is the proper storage of batteries. Currently there is no standard EU law on battery storage, only the Netherlands has specific guideline for the safe handling of Energy Storage Systems and storage of lithium batterie and accumulators. PGS 37 [49] is legally effective as of 2024. "PGS" stands for "Publicatiereeks Gevaarlijke Stoffen", which is "Hazardous Substances Publication Series." The specific requirements and measures should be properly applied to minimize the chance of an incident and its consequences. It is reasonable to expect that the coming EU law will be based on or derived from PGS37-2 Dutch regulation.

The PGS 37 guideline is drafted by a team of industry and government representatives. The existing rules for the transport of lithium batteries (ADR) have been extended as much as possible to the storage of batteries. The guideline is divided into two parts, PGS 37-1 and PGS 37-2. PGS 37-1 focuses on the safe handling of on-site energy storage systems, which have a capacity of at least 20 kWh. This section emphasizes local safety aspects and interaction with the environment. It is especially relevant for battery installers of residents, municipalities and emergency services. PGS 37-2 addresses the storage of lithium-containing energy carriers. It is a detailed set of rules and regulations to minimize the risks surrounding lithium-ion batteries and ensure safety when storing hazardous materials. PGS 37-2 applies to any company that temporarily store the lithium-containing energy carriers which include batteries and accumulators for appliances and vehicles,

such as phones, laptops, e-bikes and hybrid or full-electric cars. The requirements apply to storage in sheds and warehouses, as well as in showrooms for electric cars and bicycles, for example:

- New products. This includes, for example, sellers of (products containing) lithium batteries and accumulators.
- In-service products. This includes, for example, construction companies that work with lithium batteries and store them temporarily when they are out of service.
- Defective end-of-life batteries and accumulators. This includes collection, sorting and recycling companies.

The measures to store batteries and accumulators safely described in PGS 37-2 have four goals:

- Environmental safety (Preventing unusual occurrences and limiting their impact on the environment with a view to ensuring safety for the environment)
- Fire prevention
- Occupational safety (Preventing accidents involving hazardous substances, and reducing their consequences and preventing acute exposure of workers to hazardous substances)
- Disaster relief (Limiting the consequences of a fire or disaster and ensuring effective disaster response)

In brief, the PGS 37-2 covers:

- Safety measures: This includes the physical requirements for the storage site, such as fire-resistant properties, ventilation, and distance from other objects.
- Organizational measures: Procedures and policies for the safe storage and management of LIBs.

It is important that personnel are aware of and adhere to the guideline. For example, when used (packed) batteries are moved to a collection bin, it should be done with instructions and caution. In practice, it could happen that batteries are thrown into a collection bin too roughly during handling, causing a fire. An organizational measure under PGS 37-2 is therefore to train personnel in the safe handling of lithium (-ion) batteries, including proper procedures in case of incidents.

- Risk analysis: A systematic approach to identifying and mitigating potential hazards.
- Incident response: Guidelines for dealing with emergencies such as fire, spills or other emergencies.
- Environmental issues: Regulations to prevent environmental damage, such as the containment of any releases.

Regulations impose strict criteria for the storage of energy carriers containing lithium. These include specific requirements such as preferred ground floor placement, fire compartmentation, and 60- and 90-minute fire resistance, especially when batteries are charged within the storage cabinet.

PGS 37-2 contains about 75 measures. These measures are described in Chapter 7 of PGS 37-2 [49]. They include, for example:

- The maximum weight that may be stored
- The maximum surface area of the storage area
- The maximum storage height
- The maximum temperature in the storage space
- The minimum distance between energy carriers
- Measures around fire prevention and detection

To know exactly what measures to take, one can look within which scenario that looks at the risks and safety measures per type of company, activity and situation. These scenarios can be found in Chapter 4 and Annex H of the document on PGS 37-2.

The risks and therefore the directive is relevant both in the storage of new batteries, and in the handling of old batteries. The safe collection and transport of batteries that are considered waste are conducted using an UN-approved plastic collection device containing vermiculite, packaging leaking batteries in a separate bag and/or taping off poles.

3.2.2 Storage with new, used or remanufactured batteries

Due to design, manufacture, or aging faults, new or old batteries go to thermal-runaway or there is leakage from casing. The potential consequences are:

- Temperature built-up in the battery
- Fire in the battery
- Pressure built-up or explosion of the battery
- Release of dangerous gas
- The lithium batteries must be visually inspected before the entrance to the storage facility for appropriate storage measures. The entrance inspection is performed by a skilled worker who is sufficiently skilled in lithium batteries.
- Damages to the outer packaging
- Whether the packaging has been in contact with water
- The physical state is registered whether they are used, damaged or defect
- Visible damage such as dents, cracks, swelling, open wiring
- Visible water damage such as rust
- Traces of fire damage such as soot
- Discoloration due to leakage of gas or electrolyte
- They must be stored in the UN approved packaging and within the maximum permitted gross mass of the packaging. The state of the batteries is monitored with detectors (CO, H₂, warmth and fire detection) and visually checked daily for proper actions.
- Damage to packaging for packaged batteries
- Damage to housing for unpackaged batteries
- Leakage of electrolyte
- Stability of storage such as pallet placement and stacking

The storage place should be kept dry to avoid short circuit of the batteries due to contact with water or corrosion due to moisture. The ambient temperature and humidity of the storage facility can be monitored. To prevent short circuits, batteries should not be placed directly on the bottom of the storage facility, unless batteries are stored in waterproof containers.

The storage facility can be protected against dust, dirt, airborne contamination and pests. Mechanical impact should be avoided to damage the batteries. The batteries are stored in stable scaffold and are not loaded beyond limit. The maximum height and weight of the scaffold must be followed. An evacuation alarm system is provided within the storage facility.

At the storage facility, rules and procedures are established for handling lithium batteries. At least one expert must be present who is competent in battery handling. Professional protection is provided for a safe working environment and there are enough resources to contain a battery incident. The workers at the storage facility are aware of the dangers of lithium batteries. They are trained in the technical competences of handling, prevention and containment of a battery incident. They are aware of the internal emergency plan and measures to be taken in case of irregularities.

The storage facility is in an enclosed building not accessible to unauthorized persons. The supporting structure of the building should be fire-resistant to retain its function for a limited time during a fire. The storage space is compartmented to prevent escalation to other batteries or environment at the event of a battery incident. The separation between the compartments is built with fire-resistant materials.

3.2.3 Storage outdoor

If storage of lithium batteries takes place outdoors, distance from other buildings must be considered. In addition, batteries should be stored in such a way that they are protected from the weather. For example, lithium batteries are protected from weather influences under a canopy. The roofing of the canopy is located no more than 4.5 m above the floor. The area surrounding the outdoor storage facility is provided with a rainwater drainage system.

Aside from the safety requirements summed in the previous section, the outdoor storage should be protected against lightning strikes. A risk analysis is conducted before the design of the outdoor

storage facility, where an earthing system is installed to comply with the safety standards. The storage area is enclosed by a fence or guarded by cameras and unauthorized access is prohibited.

4. Overview of current legislation related to the transport of battery waste streams in Europe

4.1 ADR regulation

ADR stands for "Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road". The ADR regulates the international transport of dangerous goods, in all countries that have ratified this treaty, it applies to cross-border transport taking place between at least two of these countries [50]. All countries of the partners of the "ReUse" project adhere to the ADR regulation (i.e., Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, France, Germany, Norway, Serbia and Switzerland). The ADR treaty has been turned into a European directive (Directive 2008/68/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 September 2008 on the inland transport of dangerous goods) and applies to all transports on the territory of the member states of the European Union [51].

According to ADR, dangerous substances and goods must be classified according to their hazard characteristics. The classification is the basis for transport conditions. The criteria for ADR classification are based on the Globally Harmonized System of classification and labelling of chemicals (GHS). The criteria of the GHS are used for production, storage and use in addition to transport. The ADR is established under the auspices of the United Nations. The ADR includes requirements for:

- Dangerous goods criteria for hazard classification
- Shipping conditions
- Requirements for packaging and tanks
- Shipping procedures, including labelling and documentation

The materials considered in the "ReUse" project that are subjected to ADR regulation for transport are classified by the UN-codes reported in Table 6.

The ADR has several UN numbers for Lithium-Ion Batteries:

UN3090, Lithium metal batteries (including lithium alloy batteries)

UN3091, Lithium metal batteries contained in equipment or packed with equipment (including lithium alloy batteries)

UN3480, Lithium-Ion-Batteries (shipped by themselves)

UN3481, Lithium-Ion-Batteries contained in equipment or packed separately with equipment (including lithium-ion polymer batteries)

UN3536, Lithium batteries installed in cargo transport unit

Table 6: UN codes of materials relevant within the "ReUse" project that are classified under the ADR regulation.

UN No.	Name and description	Class	Classification code	Packaging group	Labels	Special provisions	Limited and excepted quantities		Packaging			Portable tanks and bulk containers		ADR tank		Vehicle for tank carriage	Transport category (Tunnel restriction code)	Special provisions for carriage				Hazard identification No.
							(7a)	(7b)	Packaging instructions	Special packaging provisions	Mixed packaging provisions	Instructions	Special provisions	Tank code	Special provisions			Packages	Bulk	Loading, unloading and handling	Operation	
(1)	(2)	(3a)	(3b)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7a)	(7b)	(8)	(9a)	(9b)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)	(17)	(18)	(19)	(20)
1077	PROPYLENE	2	2F		2.1	662	0	E0	P200		MP9	(M) T50		PxBN (M)	TA4 TT9	FL	2 (B/D)			CV9 CV10 CV36	S2 S20	23
1010	BUTADIENES, STABILIZED or BUTADIENES AND HYDROCARBON MIXTURE, STABILIZED, containing more than 40% butadienes	2	2F		2.1	386 618 662 676	0	E0	P200		MP9	(M) T50		PxBN (M)	TA4 TT9	FL	2 (B/D)	V8		CV9 CV10 CV36	S2 S4 S20	239
1161	DIMETHYL CARBONATE	3	F1	II	3		1 L	E2	P001 IBC02 R001		MP19	T4	TP1	LGBF		FL	2 (D/E)				S2 S20	33
1234	METHYLAL	3	F1	II	3		5 L	E2	P001 IBC02	B8	MP19	T7	TP2	L1.5B N		FL	2 (D/E)				S2 S20	33
1362	CARBON, ACTIVATED	4.2	S2	III	4.2	646	0	E1	P002 IBC08 LP02 R001	PP11 B3	MP14	T1	TP33	SGAV		AT	4 (E)	V1	VC1 VC2 AP1		40	
1922	PYRROLIDINE	3	FC	II	3 +8		1 L	E2	P001 IBC02		MP19	T7	TP1	L4BH		FL	2 (D/E)				S2 S20	338

1962	ETHYLENE	2	2F		2.1	662	0	E0	P200		MP9	(M)		PxBN(M)	TA4 TT9	FL	2 (B/D)			CV9 CV10 CV36	S2 S20	23	
2055	STYRENE MONOMEER, STABILIZED	3	F1	III	3	386 676	5 L	E1	P001 IBC03		MP19	T2	TP1	LGBF		FL	3 (D/E)	V8 V12			S2 S4	39	
2366	DIETHYL CARBONATE	3	F1	III	3		5 L	E1	9001 IBC03 LP01 R001		MP19	T2	TP1	LGBF		FL	3 (D/E)	V12			S2	30	
2923	CORROSIVE SOLID, TOXIC, N.O.S.	8	CT2	II	8 + 6.1	274	1 kg	E2	P002 IBC05		MP18	T6	TP33	S10AN L10BH		AT	1 (E)	V10		CV13 CV28		86	
3077	ENVIRONMENTALLY HAZARDOUS SUBSTANCE, SOLID, N.O.S.	9	M7	III	9	274 335 375 601	5 kg	E1	P002 IBC08 LP02 R001	PP12 B3	MP10	T1 BK1 BK2 BK3	TP33	SGAV LGBV		AT	3 (-)	V13	VC1 VC2	CV13		90	
3082	ENVIRONMENTALLY HAZARDOUS SUBSTANCE, LIQUID, N.O.S.	9	M6	III	9	274 335 375 601	5 L	E1	P001 IBC03 LP01 R001	PP1	MP19 T4	T4	TP1 TP29	LGBV		AT	3 (-)	V12		CV13		90	
3480	LITHIUM ION BATTERIES (including lithium ion polymer batteries)	9	M4		9A	188 230 310 348 376 377 387 636	0	E0	P903 P908 P909 P910 P911 LP903 LP904 LP905 LP906								2 (E)						
3481	LITHIUM ION BATTERIES CONTAINED IN EQUIPMENT or LITHIUM ION BATTERIES PACKED WITH EQUIPMENT (including lithium ion polymer batteries)	9	M4		9A	188 230 310 348 360 376 377 387 390 670	0	E0	P903 P908 P909 P910 P911 LP903 LP904 LP905 LP906									2 (E)					

In this section, the main considerations and actions to be taken when shipping a material according to the ADR regulation are discussed. As a main example the shipment of LIBs is used, whereby the general practises apply to all ADR regulated materials. Whereas the specific transport prescriptions per material, as given in Table 6, need to be applied.

A cell or battery can be defined as follows:

- Cell: a single encased electro-chemical unit which exhibits a voltage differential across the positive and negative terminals
- Battery: two or more cells connected electrically together and fitted with devices necessary for use
- Battery pack: any set of primary or rechargeable cells or batteries that are connected and/or encapsulated within an outer casing to form a complete unit that the end-user is not intended to split up or open.

The lithium batteries differ by the nature and composition of the electrode's materials, the substances in the electrolyte and the capacity to convert chemical energy into electricity (see Table 7 for nominal capacities and voltages by battery chemistry type). The lithium battery classification has been reduced to two groups:

- Lithium metal batteries contain lithium in the metallic form. They have lithium metal or lithium compounds as an anode. They are primary cells used in small consumer electrical appliances such as watches, cameras, calculators etc. The lithium content in grams needs to be determined.
- Lithium-ion batteries contain lithium in the ionic form. They are rechargeable batteries used in consumer electronics, such as mobile phones, laptops, tablets, power tools, electric vehicles or bikes, energy storage systems. The power rating in Wh needs to be determined.

Table 7. Nominal capacity and voltages per battery chemistry type.

Chemistry	Nominal mAh	Nominal voltage	Equivalent lithium content per cell	Nominal Wh
LFP	1300mAh	3.2V	0.39g	4.15Wh
NMC/NCA/LCO	2600mAh	3.6V	0.78g	9.36Wh
NMC/NCA	3500mAh	3.7V	1.05g	12.95Wh

LIBs, regardless of their composition, are rated as a hazardous substance by the United Nations worldwide. They are defined as M4 substances under Class 9 (Miscellaneous dangerous substances and articles) in Chapter 2.2.9. They must therefore comply with laws governing the transportation of hazardous materials by road, rail, water and air. LIBs must in any case meet the requirements of each test from the Manual of Tests and Criteria, Part III, subsection 38.3 and have a certificate thereof.

Each shipment must have a LIB sticker showing the UN number preceded by the letters "UN". In the case of lithium-ion cells or batteries, this is 'UN 3480'. If the cells or batteries are included in or packaged with equipment, then UN number 3481 must be shown. Li-ion cells and batteries, if built into equipment, must be protected against damage and short circuits, and the equipment must be equipped with effective means to prevent accidental activation.

Cells and batteries must be protected to prevent short circuits. This includes protection against contact with conductive materials within the same packaging that could lead to a short circuit.

- Individual protection of the battery terminals
- Inner packaging to prevent contact between cells and batteries
- Batteries with recessed terminals designed to protect against short circuits
- The use of an electrically non-conductive and non-combustible cushioning material to fill empty space between the cells or batteries in the packaging.

According to these regulations, LIBs must be provided with their own labelling and packaging instructions. The requirements for the packaging:

- Packaging is manufactured, reconditioned and tested under a quality assurance program.
- Packaging is strong enough to withstand the shocks and loadings normally encountered during carriage.
- Packaging is constructed and closed to prevent any loss of contents by vibration or changes in temperature, humidity or pressure.
- Batteries are packed only in inner packagings placed in suitable outer packagings. Intermediate packagings may be used.

The requirements for the labelling:

- The UN number preceded by the letters “UN” are clearly and durably marked on each package.
- The labelling is readily visible and legible and can withstand open weather exposure without a substantial reduction in effectiveness.

The labels are given a UN number and are also equipped with a battery symbol. The minimum size for these labels is 100 mm by 100 mm. The sticker shall be in the shape of a rectangle with shaded borders. The dimensions shall be at least 120 mm wide × 110 mm high. The minimum width of the shading shall be 5 mm. The symbol shall be black on a white or suitable contrasting background. The shading is red.

Any carriage of dangerous goods is accompanied by the documentation:

- Dangerous goods description in sequence UN n. / shipping name / label model (class) / Packing Group
- The number and a description of the packages
- The total quantity of each item of dangerous goods
- The name and address of the sender
- The name and address of the receiver
- Date and signature

To determine which special provision applicable to certain articles or substances (ADR Chapter 3.2 Column 6 Table A) to follow the shipment of lithium batteries, the equivalent lithium content

per cell needs to be calculated. The general formula to calculate the equivalent lithium content is: Ah per cell x 0.3 g.

Below the special provisions related to UN3480 and UN3481 are given, which can be important when shipping small quantities of research samples within the “ReUse” project.

The materials that are shipped between the partners of the "ReUse" project are:

- EOL batteries from LMT, ESS or EV
- Production waste battery, including waste electrodes and dry/wet reject cells
- The binder, electrolyte
- Black mass
- Carbon black, cathode/anode materials
- Battery prototypes

We take all practicable steps to ensure that shipment is managed in a manner that will protect human health, the climate and the environment against adverse effects. The following sections list the requirements of shipment and labels of these materials in detail after the summary table.

Table 8. Summary of shipment requirements for the materials in the “ReUse” project.

Items	UN code	ADR provision	Transport limit	Transport code
Lithium-ion cell <20Wh/cell	3480	188	30 kg	
Waste lithium-ion cell >20Wh/cell batteries >100Wh/battery transported as new	3480			P903
Waste lithium-ion cell >20Wh/cell batteries >100Wh/battery for disposal or recycling	3480		30 kg	P909
Waste cells and batteries contained in equipment for disposal or recycling			333 kg	P909
Pre-production prototypes		310	100 cells	P910
Mixture of solids – production waste	3077	335		
Black mass sample	3077	335 375	5 kg	

4.1.1 Lithium-ion cell <20 Wh/cell (cfr. special provision 188)

Waste lithium-ion cells which meet the test requirements with a power rating not exceeding 20 Wh/cell are small cells partially exempted. They are transported under the special provision of 188 with a label of UN 3480. The requirements include:

- Prerequisite: cells must meet the test requirements
- Exemption conditions:
 - Cells are protected to prevent short circuit or contact with conductive materials
 - Cells are packed in inner packaging that completely enclose the cell
 - The inner packaging is packed in strong outer packaging
 - Packaging can withstand a 1.2 m drop test in any orientation without damage or shifting to cells
 - Weight limit is 30 kg gross
- Transport document is not required.

4.1.2 Waste lithium-ion cell >20Wh/cell batteries >100Wh/battery transported as new

The definition of “waste batteries” means that there is no direct use envisaged but are transported for reprocessing, dumphing, elimination by incineration or other methods of disposal.

Waste lithium-ion cells with a power rating more than 20 Wh/cell or waste lithium-ion batteries with a power rating more than 100 Wh/battery can be transported with labels of UN 3480 and class 9. The transport mode of P903 must be followed.

- Cells and batteries are protected against short circuit (terminals bound and covered with isolation tape or plastic caps, and/or wrapped individual bags)
- Cells and batteries are packed conforming to Packing Group II performance level
- Cells and batteries are protected against damage under normal conditions of transport
- Batteries containing cells connected in parallel are protected against reverse current flow
- Batteries manufactured after 31 December 2011 are marked with Wh rating on the outside case

4.1.3 Waste lithium-ion cell >20Wh/cell batteries >100Wh/battery for disposal or recycling

Waste lithium-ion cells with a power rating more than 20 Wh/cell or waste lithium-ion batteries with a power rating more than 100 Wh/battery can be transported for recycling with a weight limit of 30 kg gross with labels of UN 3480 and class 9. The transport mode of P909 must be followed.

- The weight limit is 30 kg gross
- Cells and batteries are protected against short circuit (battery terminals are individually protected)
- Inner packaging to prevent contact between cells and batteries
- The use of a non-conductive and non-combustible cushioning material to fill empty space between the cells or batteries in the packaging
- Cells and batteries are secured within the outer packaging to protect against excessive movement during carriage.
- The strong outer packaging meets the general provision of packaging but need not to be approved
- Metal packaging is fitted with a non-conductive lining material like plastics of adequate strength for the intended use

Marking of packages is “LITHIUM BATTERIES FOR DISPOSAL” or “LITHIUM BATTERIES FOR RECYCLING”.

4.1.4 Waste cells and batteries contained in equipment for disposal or recycling

Waste lithium-ion batteries contained in equipment from private households are collected and carried for dismantling, recycling or disposal. They are not subject to ADR if the total amount of lithium cells and batteries per transport unit does not exceed 333 kg and the equipment is packed:

- In accordance with packing instruction P909

It is packed in strong outer packaging which meet the following requirements:

- Not approved packaging, constructed of suitable material and of adequate strength and design in relation to the packaging capacity and its intended use.
- Appropriate measures are taken to minimize the damage of the equipment when filling and handling the packaging.
- The packaging is constructed and closed to prevent any loss of content.
- Packages are marked with “LITHIUM BATTERIES FOR DISPOSAL” or “LITHIUM BATTERIES FOR RECYCLING” and are transported under the special provision of 670(b).

4.1.5 Pre-production prototypes (cfr. special provision 310)

The testing requirements in sub-section 38.3 of the Manual of Tests and Criteria do not apply to production runs consisting of not more than 100 cells and batteries, or to pre-production prototypes of lithium cells or batteries when these prototypes are transported for testing.

Special provision 310 covers the exemptions from the testing requirements under the Road and Maritime transport modes. The transport document shall include the statement: “Transport in accordance with special provision 310”.

They must be packed according to Packing Instruction P910, using only approved packaging conforming to Packing Group II performance level. The Packing requirements include

- Each cell of battery is individually packed in an inner packaging and placed inside an outer package.
- Each inner packaging is surrounded by sufficient non-combustible non-conductive thermal insulation material.
- The outer packaging belongs to a tested design type, for boxes 4A, 4B, 4N, 4C1, 4C2, 4D, 4F, 4G, 4H1, 4H2.

4.1.6 Mixture of solids – production waste (cfr. special provision 335)

The cathode or anode waste is chemically stable under normal conditions, but one should avoid spark or flame, excess heat or fire, dust formation, or exposure to moist air or water. During storage or transportation, direct contact with strong oxidizing or reducing agents must be avoided. Waste cells should be separated to prevent short-circuiting and packed in a strong package during transport. They are offered for transport at a state of charge (SoC) not exceeding 30% of their rated design capacity.

The production waste is a mixture of solids and can be shipped under UN3077, if no free liquid is visible at the time of loading or packaging. The transport unit should be leakproof.

4.1.7 Black mass sample (cfr. special provision 335 and 375)

The special provision 335 and 375 cover the mixture of solids that are environmentally hazardous but not subject to the requirements of ADR. Black mass samples, which are mixtures of solids, can be shipped under UN3077 (Environmentally hazardous substance, solid, N.O.S.), if no free liquid is visible at the time of loading or packaging. The transport unit should be leakproof.

If free liquid is visible at the time the mixture is loaded, the mixture shall be classified as UN3082. However, sealed packets and articles are not subject to the requirements of ADR if they contain less than 10 ml of an environmentally hazardous liquid and absorbed into a solid material but with no free liquid in the packet.

The transport document shall include the statement: “Transport in accordance with special provision 335 and 375”. They are packed in inner packaging of 5 kg or less and the single or combination packaging meet the general provision of 4.1.1.1, 4.1.1.2 and 4.1.1.5 to 4.1.1.8.

4.1.1.1: Packagings for dangerous goods:

- Strong enough to withstand the shocks and loadings
- Constructed and closed to prevent any loss of contents
- Closed that no dangerous residue outside of packagings

4.1.1.2: Packagings in direct contact with dangerous goods

- Not affected or weakened by the dangerous goods
- No reaction with the dangerous goods
- No permeation of the dangerous goods

4.1.1.5: Inner packagings are strong enough that no puncture or leakage will occur. They are secured in outer packagings with suitable cushioning material to prevent significant movement.

4.1.1.6: Dangerous goods are not mixed and packed together.

4.1.1.7: Inner packagings are closed first.

4.1.1.8: A vent is provided if pressure may develop in a package by the emission of gas from the contents.

4.2 EU regulation 2024/1157 on shipments of waste

Recently, in April 2024, the regulation (EU) 2024/1157 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 on shipments of waste is published [52]. It applies to the shipment of waste between Member States, with or without transit through third countries.

Article 18 of this regulation outlines the general information requirements of shipments of waste.

“A shipment may only be arranged by the person who has obtained a permit or is registered.

The facility that receives the shipment has obtained a permit or registration.

All undertakings involved in the shipment are registered in the notification and movement documents to all competent authorities concerned, no later than two working days before the shipment starts.

The R-codes of the recovery operation are indicated in the document

The facility provides confirmation within two working days of receipt of the waste to the person who arranges the shipment.

The facility provides a certificate that the recovery has been completed

A contract for the shipment contains information on the person who arranges the shipment, the facility, the description of the waste, the waste identification codes, the quantity of waste covered by the contract, the recovery operation and the period of validity of the contract.”

The recovery operations defined in Annex II to Directive 2008/98/EC that could be related in the "ReUse" project:

- R2: Solvent reclamation/regeneration
- R4: Recycling/reclamation of metals and metal compounds
- R5: Recycling/reclamation of other inorganic materials
- R6: Regeneration of acids or bases
- R13: Storage of waste pending any of the recovery operations

The waste identification codes in Annex V (Annex VIII to the Basel Convention) that could be related to materials in the "ReUse" project are:

A4150: Waste chemical substances arising from research and development or teaching activities which are not identified and/or are new and whose effects on human healthy and/or the environment are not known.

B1090: Waste batteries conforming to a specification, excluding those made with lead, cadmium or mercury.

4.2.1 Laboratory analysis exempt of procedures

The regulation states in (24) that laboratory analysis and experimental treatment trials are necessary to assess the suitability for recovery or improve waste recovery. Innovative waste management operations can establish circular economy business models in the European Union. The shipment of waste for such laboratory analysis and experimental treatment trials is not subject to the applicable procedures. Moreover, to deliver accurate results for more developed waste management, a sufficiently significant quantity of waste is allowed to be shipped for the purpose of laboratory analysis and experimental treatment trials for shipments within the Union. It is indicated in Article 4 Overall procedural framework that shipments for laboratory analysis or experimental treatment trails are not subject to the general information requirements if the quantity of waste shipped is less than 20 kg.

5. Conclusion

To address the growing issues of battery waste, the "ReUse" project has emerged in response to the rapid development of LFP (Lithium Iron Phosphate) batteries, aiming to tackle the environmental and sustainability challenges posed by LFP battery waste.

This report introduces the background, main objectives, methodologies and organization of the "ReUse" project. Furthermore, it defines the different battery waste types involved in the project, detailing their identification characteristics, physical and chemical properties and the processes through which they are generated and their circulation within the project.

Additionally, this report investigates the laws and regulations related to the transportation and safety of battery waste in Europe. The section on safety regulations of battery waste covers the storage, packaging, and safety features. This information not only can serve as useful guidance for the partners of the project, but also can be used for the public and other entities about battery waste safety. The report also outlines the regulations for battery and battery materials (waste) transportation between different European countries to facilitate the project partners in the delivery and receipt of LFP batteries and their waste. In this case the ADR regulation should be adhered to for the shipment, whereas if the material is a waste material, the additional EU regulation on waste shipment needs to be adhered to.

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